

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of customer experience on loyalty through satisfaction as an intervening variable for users of maxim online transportation services in the city of semarang

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Abstract

The high level of online transportation users in Indonesia creates intense competition and to be able to survive in the midst of competition, companies must improve their performance in various aspects to be able to create a good experience for their users so that there is high satisfaction so that user loyalty to the company continues to survive and increase. This research aims to determine the influence of customer experience on user loyalty through satisfaction with users of Maxim online transportation services in Semarang City. This type of research is explanatory research with a sample size of 96 respondents who are Maxim users in Semarang City. with a sampling technique using non-probability sampling with a multistage purposive sampling method. The population in this research is the people of Semarang City who have used Maxim. The data analysis method uses SmartPLS 3.2.9 software. The research results prove that the mediating relationship between customer experience and loyalty through satisfaction as an intervening variable is partial mediation. The suggestion in this research is that Maxim is expected to pay more attention to aspects that can influence user experience so that users feel maximum satisfaction when using Maxim.

Keywords: Customer Experience; Loyalty; Satisfaction; Consumer Behavior; Online Transportation

1. Introduction

The emergence of online transportation services is a form of fulfillment to adapt to changes in consumer behavior in this digital era. With the online transportation application, people will easily order and get transportation when they want to travel easily via smartphone. With the presence of this online transportation service, people's mobility from one place to another will become more effective and efficient. This online transportation service has succeeded in attracting the attention of the Indonesian people. The high level of online transportation users in Indonesia creates opportunities for online transportation service providers to enter the market in Indonesia to meet people's needs in the transportation sector.

The large number of online transportation service companies will certainly trigger quite tight competition. Every company will certainly try to provide the best to its consumers in order to create loyalty towards using online transportation services. Creating user loyalty is one of the targets that every business must have. Loyal users will create consistency in the use of online transportation services.

DataIndonesia.id survey results show that Maxim's user loyalty level is in 3rd place, and is still behind Gojek and Grab. Based on this survey, most survey respondents have more than one online transportation application, so respondents' loyalty to Maxim is very small. Apart from that, there are reviews containing disappointment expressed through the

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Google Play platform. These reviews describe the user's experience while using Maxim. This indicates that Maxim has not been able to provide maximum satisfaction for its users so this can certainly hinder Maxim's increase in loyalty.

Customer loyalty is a form of customer commitment as a form of their loyalty by purchasing or reusing a product or service that they like now and in the future, this is of course due to the good experience they feel as a form of satisfaction with the product or service. the services they use. One aspect that can encourage users to become loyal users is the satisfaction that users feel when using Maxim. Therefore, to form loyal customers, Maxim must try hard to increase user satisfaction because user satisfaction is one aspect that can lead to user loyalty.

User satisfaction can be used as evaluation material for companies to improve aspects that are considered less satisfying to users. User satisfaction can be influenced by Customer Experience because to create satisfaction requires a good experience felt by the user, and this experience can be obtained through the price offered, the quality of service provided, as well as the ease of accessing a product or service that the user wants to meet their needs and needs. as well as their expectations.

When Maxim expands its regional network to all regions in Indonesia and continues to experience an increase in users every year, however, this increase has not shown an increase in Maxim user loyalty, because there are still many shortcomings that are complained about by its users, thus providing a less good experience for its users, so this This can have an impact on the difficulty of getting loyal users because Maxim users do not get maximum satisfaction with Maxim's performance as long as they use Maxim as online transportation.

Based on the problems related to Maxim user loyalty, the problem formulation that can be formulated and raised in this research is (1) Is there an influence between Customer Experience and User Loyalty? (2) Is there an influence between Customer Experience and User Satisfaction? (3) Is there an influence between User Satisfaction and User Loyalty? (4) Is there an influence between Customer Experience and Loyalty through User Satisfaction?

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Theory of Reasoned Action

According to Ajzen and Fishbein (1975), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) is used to study human behavior. Research in social psychology shows that a person's behavioral intention towards a particular behavior is a determining factor in whether the individual will carry out that behavior or not. The Theory of Reason Action, developed by Ajzen and Fishbein, states that the best prediction of someone's behavior is based on that person's interests. The Theory of Reason Action has two main constructs of intention, namely attitudes towards behavior and subjective norms.

2.2. Consumer Behavior

According to Engel (2010), consumer behavior is the direct actions involved in obtaining, consuming and consuming products and services, including the processes that precede and follow these actions. Meanwhile, according to Solomon (2011), consumer behavior is a process that occurs when a consumer chooses to buy, use, or dispose of a product, service, idea, or experience to satisfy the consumer's desires and meet the consumer's needs. Factors that influence consumer behavior according to Kotler (2001) are culture, social factors, personal factors and psychological factors.

2.3. Buying Decision

According to Kotler and Keller (2009), purchasing decisions are consumer decisions regarding preferences for brands in a collection of choices. The specific purchasing decision process according to Kotler and Armstrong (2008) consists of a sequence of events:

- Problem Recognition
- Information Search
- Alternative Evaluation
- Purchase Decision
- Post-Purchase Behavior
- Loyalty

According to Hasan (2014) Customer loyalty is consumers who make repeat purchases or use services repeatedly and regularly to satisfy their desires. Kotler and Keller (2016) explain that customer loyalty is a deeply held commitment to

repurchase a product or service they like in the future. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), there are 3 indicators of customer loyalty:

- Repeat purchases,
- Retention
- Referrals.

2.4. Satisfaction

Kotler (2002) explains that user satisfaction can be interpreted as the level of a user's feelings as a result of a comparison between the user's expectations for a product and the actual results obtained by the user from the product. According to Lupiyoadi (2001) customer satisfaction is the level of feeling where someone expresses the results of a comparison of the performance of the service product received with what was expected. Lupiyoadi (2001) explains that there are four indicators to determine the level of consumer satisfaction:

- Product Quality
- Price
- Service Quality
- Convenience

2.5. Customer Experience

According to Lemke et al. (2006), Customer Experience is a perception that is closely related to the results of interactions that are felt to achieve customer goals and defines experience quality as a perceived assessment of the excellence or superiority of the customer experience. According to Lemke et al. (2006) there are 8 indicators related to Customer Experience:

- Accessibility
- Competence
- Customer Recognition
- Helpfulness
- Personalization
- Problem Solving
- Promise Fulfillment
- Value For Time

2.6. Research Method

This research is an explanatory research type using an approach. The sampling technique used is non-probability using multistage sampling in order to obtain a proportional sample quota. The population in this study were Maxim users in Semarang City with a research sample of 96 respondents with respondent criteria determined using a purposive sampling technique. Then, the data in this research was obtained through an offline questionnaire with a measurement scale using a Likert scale. The data analysis technique used in this research is using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) technique or method which includes two tests, namely Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model) and Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model) which are processed using Smart-PLS software 3.2.9 for windows.

Figure 1 Hypothesis Model

2.7. Hypothesis

2.7.1. *The influence of Customer Experience on Satisfaction*

Research by Rita and Fabiola Meike Trimulyani (2022) entitled “The Influence of Customer Experience and Brand Image on Customers Satisfaction and its Impact on Customer Loyalty” shows the results that Customer Experience has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

H1: There is an influence between Customer Experience and Satisfaction.

2.7.2. *The influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty*

Research by Alia Presilia Larasati and Farah Oktafani (2020) entitled “The Influence of Customer Experience and Brand Awareness on Gojek Customer Loyalty in Bandung City in 2019” shows the results that Customer Experience and brand awareness variables simultaneously and partially have a significant effect on loyalty. Research by Arrasyi Sabda Ramadhan (2022) entitled “The influence of customer experience and perceived price on customer loyalty which is mediated by customer satisfaction with online taxi services” also shows the results that There is a positive influence of Customer Experience on customer loyalty.

H2: There is an influence between Customer Experience and Loyalty.

2.7.3. *The influence of satisfaction on loyalty*

Research by Delvia Safitri and Annur Fitri Hayati (2022) entitled “The Influence of Price and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty Through Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable for Maxim Online Services” shows the results that Customer Satisfaction has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty.

H3: There is an influence between satisfaction and loyalty.

2.7.4. *The influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty through Satisfaction*

Research by Agustiono, Sari Listyorini, and Hari Susanta Nugraha (2023) entitled “The Influence of Customer Experience on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable (Study in the Semarang Community of LinkAja Users)” shows the results that The Customer Experience variable has a significant influence on Loyalty with Satisfaction as an intervening variable with a positive influence..

H4: There is an influence between Customer Experience on Loyalty and Satisfaction as an intervening variable.

3. Result

3.1. Convergent Validity

Validity testing via Convergent Validity can be seen from the loading factor value of each item and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value of each variable. An item can be said to be valid if the outer loading value is >0.70 and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value is >0.50 .

In the first iteration, there was still an outer loading value below 0.70. The CE.6 item with a score of 0.277 is considered ineligible because the score is <0.70 so the item must be deleted. Conclusions regarding Convergent Validity cannot be obtained because there are still items that are not yet valid, therefore a second iteration is needed regarding outer loading by discarding items with a value below 0.70.

Figure 2 First iteration

Figure 3 Second iteration

Table 1 Score of Average Variance Extracted

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Customer Experience	0.536
Satisfaction	0.560
Loyalty	0.541

The AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value for each variable has met the requirements, namely > 0.50 , so it can be said that the validity testing value via Convergent Validity has been met and can be continued to the next stage.

3.2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity can be said to be fulfilled if the correlation value between the indicators on the latent variable is greater than the correlation with other variables. Validity testing through the Discriminant Validity stage can be seen in Cross Loading and the AVE root value in the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 2 Score of Cross Loading

	Customer Experience	Satisfaction	Loyalty
CE.1	0.719	0.401	0.261
CE.2	0.719	0.444	0.371
CE.3	0.734	0.521	0.311
CE.4	0.750	0.514	0.315
CE.5	0.738	0.575	0.434
CE.7	0.719	0.473	0.339
CE.8	0.709	0.488	0.424
CE.9	0.733	0.540	0.389
CE.10	0.781	0.592	0.491
CE.11	0.705	0.489	0.271
CE.12	0.733	0.520	0.396
CE.13	0.724	0.518	0.235
CE.14	0.721	0.563	0.355
CE.15	0.774	0.620	0.416
CE.16	0.717	0.526	0.414
KP.1	0.508	0.778	0.380
KP.2	0.527	0.790	0.324
KP.3	0.479	0.725	0.301
KP.4	0.512	0.705	0.330
KP.5	0.620	0.802	0.460
KP.6	0.587	0.738	0.438
KP.7	0.524	0.720	0.404
KP.8	0.496	0.720	0.325
LP.1	0.449	0.509	0.768
LP.2	0.407	0.332	0.722
LP.3	0.407	0.355	0.768
LP.4	0.327	0.341	0.716
LP.5	0.328	0.327	0.732
LP.6	0.241	0.288	0.703

Based on this data, it can be seen that this stage has an appropriate cross loading value, namely that a construct with its own variables has a maximum loading relationship compared to other variables.

Based on this data, it can be seen that the root of AVE in each construct has a value that is greater than the correlation between other variables. It can be concluded that the results of Discriminant Validity testing via the Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Cross Loading are both in accordance with the provisions and are considered good or valid so that testing can be continued at the next stage.

Table 3 Score of Fornell-larcker Criterion

	Customer Experience	Satisfaction	Loyalty
Customer Experience	0.732		
Satisfaction	0.716	0.748	
Loyalty	0.503	0.502	0.735

3.3. Reliability Test

Reliability testing is a way to see the level of consistency and trustworthiness of a question item so that the item can be considered reliable. There are two stages for carrying out reliability testing, namely using Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha.

Table 4 Score of Composite Reliability dan Cronbach's alpha

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Customer Experience	0.938	0.945
Satisfaction	0.888	0.910
Loyalty	0.833	0.876

Based on this data, it can be seen that the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha values for each variable have met the requirements, namely exceeding the value of 0.70. In accordance with the results shown, it can be said that the available question items are stable and have high consistency so that the three variables are considered reliable or their reliability has been met.

3.4. R-Squared

In the Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model) test, R square is a value that shows how much the independent (exogenous) variable influences the dependent (endogenous) variable. The R square value is expected to be between 0 and 1.

Table 5 Score of R-Squared

	R Square
Loyalty	0.294
Satisfaction	0.512

Based on this data, it can be seen that the influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty is 0.294, this shows that the dependent variable Loyalty that can be explained by Customer Experience is 29.4% while the remaining 70.6% is described by other variables that were not studied. The influence of Customer Experience on Satisfaction is 0.512, this shows that the dependent variable Satisfaction that can be explained by Customer Experience is 51.2% while the remaining 48.8% is explained by other variables that were not studied.

3.5. F-Squared Effect Size

F-Squared effect size is a processing stage carried out to determine the magnitude of the influence that the independent variable has on the dependent variable. F-Squared effect size has three value categories: small (≥ 0.02), medium (≥ 0.15), and large (≥ 0.35).

Based on this data, it can be seen that there is a large effect size on the influence of Customer Experience on Satisfaction, namely 1.049 or >0.35 . Apart from that, there is a small effect size on the influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty (0.60) and the influence of Satisfaction on Loyalty (0.58).

Table 6 Score of F-Squared effect size

	Customer Experience	Satisfaction	Loyalty
Customer Experience		1.049	0.060
Satisfaction			0.058
Loyalty			

3.6. Q-Squared

Through the Q-Square stage, it will be known how good the resulting observation value is using the blindfolding procedure by looking at the Q-square value or the Predictive relevance test, which is a test carried out to show how good the resulting observation value is. If the Q-square value > 0 then it can be said to have a good observation value, whereas if the Q-square value < 0 then it can be said that the observation value is not good.

Table 7 Score of Q-Squared

	Q ²
Customer Experience	0.463
Satisfaction	0.350
Loyalty	0.422

Based on these data, it can be seen that the Q-Squared value of this research has a good/good observation value because the Q-Squared value is > 0 (zero) for the three variables, namely the Customer Experience (0.463), Satisfaction (0.350), and Loyalty (0.422).

3.7. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is testing each hypothesis that has been previously determined, namely H1, H2, H3, and H4, the results of this hypothesis, are obtained based on the significance value to determine the influence between the variables. This hypothesis test was carried out by looking at the T-Statistic and P-Value values in bootstrapping calculations.

Figure 4 Diagram Path

Table 8 Direct and Indirect Effect on the result of Path Coefficient

	Path coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Values	Description
Direct effect				
Customer Experience -> Satisfaction	0.716	12.216	0.000	H1 accepted
Customer Experience -> Loyalty	0.295	2.037	0.042	H2 accepted
Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.290	2.328	0.020	H3 accepted
Indirect effect				
Customer Experience -> Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.208	2.142	0.033	H4 accepted

Based on table 8 above, the conclusions that can be drawn are:

H1: The test results prove that the Path Coefficient of the Customer Experience variable on Satisfaction has a positive effect with a value of 0.716, a T-Statistic value of 12,216 or > table score 1.98, and a P-Value of 0.000 < sig number. 5%. This research proves that the Customer Experience variable has a significant positive influence on satisfaction. So it can be concluded that H1 states "There is an influence between Customer Experience and Satisfaction." Accepted.

H2: The test results prove that the Path Coefficient of the Customer Experience variable on Satisfaction has a positive effect with a value of 0.295, a T-Statistic value of 2.037 or > table score 1.98, and a P-Value of 0.042 < sig number. 5%. This research proves that the Customer Experience variable has a significant positive influence on Loyalty. So it can be concluded that H2 states "There is an influence between Customer Experience and Loyalty." Accepted.

H3: The test results prove that the Path Coefficient of the Satisfaction with Loyalty variable has a positive effect with a value of 0.290, a T-Statistic value of 2.328 or > table score 1.98, and a P-Value of 0.020 < sig number. 5%. This research proves that the Satisfaction variable has a significant positive influence on Loyalty. So it can be concluded that H3 states "There is an influence between satisfaction and loyalty." Accepted.

H4: The test results prove that the test results of the indirect influence of the Customer Experience variable on Loyalty through Satisfaction have a positive effect with a value of 0.208, a T-Statistic value of 2.142 or > table score 1.98, and a P-value of 0.033 < sig number. 5%. This research proves that the Customer Experience variable has a significant positive influence on Loyalty through Satisfaction. So it can be concluded that H4 which states "There is an influence between Customer Experience on Loyalty through Satisfaction" is accepted. Because both direct effect and indirect effect show significant results, the mediation relationship of satisfaction as a mediating variable of customer experience on loyalty is partial mediation.

The Mediation Test using the Variance Accounted For (VAF) Method is used to determine how much the intervening variable is able to influence the independent variable on the dependent variable. Before calculating the mediation effect using the VAF method, the direct effect and indirect effect test results must first be significant.

The following is the VAF calculation formula:

$$VAF = \frac{\text{Indirect Effect (b.c)}}{\text{Direct Effect (a) + Indirect Effect (b.c)}}$$

$$VAF = \frac{0.716 \times 0.290}{0.295 + (0.716 \times 0.290)}$$

$$VAF = \frac{0.208}{0.295 + 0.208} = 0,413$$

Based on the calculations above, it can be concluded that the mediation relationship between the Customer Experience variable and the Loyalty through Satisfaction variable is Partial Mediation because the resulting VAF value is 0.413 or $20\% \leq 41.3\% \leq 80\%$.

Table 9 Total Effect

Direct effect	Path coefficient
Customer Experience -> Satisfaction	0.716
Customer Experience -> Loyalty	0.295
Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.290
Indirect effect	
Customer Experience -> Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.208
Total Effect	
Customer Experience -> Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.503

Based on this data, it can be seen that the total influence of the indirect influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty through Satisfaction is greater than the direct influence of Customer Experience on Loyalty. This shows that Customer Experience can have a significant influence on Loyalty directly, but with Satisfaction as an intervening variable it will have a greater influence on Loyalty. Therefore, satisfaction needs to be paid attention to because it can bridge loyalty to a greater extent than Customer Experience towards Loyalty directly.

4. Discussion

This research has succeeded in proving the first hypothesis because the research results show that the influence of Customer Experience on Satisfaction has a significant positive effect. This research proves that the Customer Experience variable obtained by Maxim online transportation service users has a positive influence on satisfaction. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Alia Presilia Larasati and Farah Oktafani (2020) and Arrasyi Sabda Ramadhan (2022) which produced a significant relationship between Customer Experience and Loyalty. This means that the better and more satisfying the experience felt by users, the more loyalty they will be able to create in using online transportation services.

This research has succeeded in proving the second hypothesis because the research results show that the influence of the Customer Experience variable on Loyalty has a significant positive effect. This research proves that the Customer Experience variable obtained by Maxim online transportation service users has an influence on Loyalty in a positive direction. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Alia Presilia Larasati and Farah Oktafani (2020) which produced a significant relationship between Customer Experience and Loyalty. This means that the better and more satisfying the experience felt by users, the more loyal they will be to using online transportation services.

This research has succeeded in proving the second hypothesis because the research results show that the influence of the Satisfaction variable on Loyalty has a significant positive effect. This research proves that the Satisfaction variable has a positive influence on Loyalty. This is in line with previous research conducted by Delvia Safitri and Annur Fitri Hayati (2022) which also proves that there is a significant influence between satisfaction and user loyalty. This means that the higher the satisfaction felt by Maxim users, the more user loyalty towards Maxim will be created or increased.

The results of the path coefficient test in the fourth hypothesis show two relationships, namely a direct relationship (Direct Effect) between Customer Experience and Loyalty which has a positive effect on the test results. This shows that the Customer Experience obtained by users of Maxim's online transportation services has a significant positive influence on Loyalty. Next is the indirect relationship (Indirect Effect) from Customer Experience to Loyalty through Satisfaction which has a positive relationship. The mediating relationship between Customer Experience and Loyalty through Satisfaction is Partial Mediation because whether or not Satisfaction is an intervening variable, the correlation between Customer Experience and Loyalty will remain meaningful. This is also supported by the results of the mediation test using the VAF method which gives the result that the mediation relationship between the Customer Experience variable and the Loyalty variable through Satisfaction is Partial Mediation.

5. Conclusion

The Customer Experience variable has a positive and significant influence on the Satisfaction variable. This can be interpreted as meaning that the better the experience felt by the user, the greater the satisfaction felt by the user.

The Customer Experience variable has a positive and significant influence on the Loyalty variable. This can be interpreted as meaning that the better the user experience, the greater the user's loyalty to Maxim.

The Satisfaction variable has a positive and significant influence on the Loyalty variable. This can be interpreted as the high level of satisfaction felt by users, which will also increase user loyalty to Maxim.

The Customer Experience variable (X) has a significant influence on Loyalty (Y) with Satisfaction (Z) as an intervening variable with a positive influence. This shows that the better the experience felt by Maxim users, the more satisfaction it will create for users so that they become loyal users. The mediating relationship between Customer Experience (X) and Loyalty (Y) through Satisfaction (Z) is Partial Mediation because whether or not there is E-Satisfaction as an intervening variable, the correlation between Customer Experience (X) and Loyalty (Y) will remain meaningful.

Suggestions

In the research results related to the Customer Experience variable, there are still item values that are below average. One of the lowest is the Problem Solving indicator, Maxim can increase its agility in resolving problems that frequently become complaints from users. In the Accessibility indicator, Maxim is expected to be able to improve the navigation system used or collaborate with navigation systems such as Google Maps whose quality is guaranteed. The company must always pay attention to these things in order to maintain user comfort so that users can have a better experience when using Maxim.

In the research results related to the Satisfaction variable, there are still item values that are below average. For example, the Convenience item is related to the ease of getting a Maxim driver. Regarding this, Maxim can take into account the level of demand and the number of drivers in several areas and is expected to expand or add drivers to areas where Maxim drivers are still minimal.

The results of this research found that the majority of respondents were interested in other online transportation services. To overcome this problem, Maxim can provide attractive offers not only for new users, but also for old users by providing special promo codes for old users. so that users persist in using Maxim

Compliance with ethical standards

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The authors have declared that no competing interest exists.

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